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LOC107984343, a TE differentiation-associated product.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of LOC107984343, a TE differentiation-associated product, as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.